

Cross-disciplinary and Cross-departmental Impacts on Developing Modular Product Families - Current and Future Challenges

Marc Zuefle¹, Christoph Rennpferdt², Dieter Krause³

¹Hamburg University of Technology (TUHH), Institute for Product Development and Mechanical Engineering Design; marc.zuefle@tuhh.de, corresponding author

²Hamburg University of Technology (TUHH), Institute for Product Development and Mechanical Engineering Design; christoph.rennpferdt@tuhh.de

³Hamburg University of Technology (TUHH), Institute for Product Development and Mechanical Engineering Design; krause@tuhh.de

Abstract

This research is based on an industry survey conducted on challenges, influences and potentials in product development through cross-departmental and cross-disciplinary architectures. This paper addresses the second part of the survey, that explicitly addresses the influences of these architectures on the development of modular product families. Different questions posed to a broad group of participants were aimed at considering various challenges, influences and potentials to product development in the context of modular product families. In addition, the identified challenges, influences and potentials were considered in relation to the interactions of different development disciplines (cross-disciplinary) and different product life phases (cross-departmental). By taking a comprehensive look at the different perspectives, added value for the cross-disciplinary and cross-departmental development of modular product families can be identified and further steps towards mapping these structures can be derived.

Introduction

Manufacturing companies are facing a high competitive pressure due to long-term megatrends such as an increasing globalization, a growing demand for individual products and an accelerating technological progress (Krause et al. 2014; Krause und Gebhardt 2018). To cope with this, many companies are diversifying their external variety to offer additional product variants. However, in the long term, this strategy leads to an increase in internal variety, an increase in variety-induced complexity and thus also in costs (Blecker und Abdelkafi 2006; Ripperda und Krause 2017). The development of modular product families is frequently cited in the literature as a solution to this challenge, as it allows a large external variety to be configured from a small number of internal product components (Otto et al. 2016; Krause und Gebhardt 2018). Since modular product families have different effects in each life phase (Hackl et al. 2020), it is a cross-departmental task to develop them. At the same time, products consist no longer of mechanical components only, but are usually mechatronic systems with electronic and software parts or so-called Product-Service Systems, which are composed of product and service components (Isaksson et al. 2009). As a consequence of this change in product composition, existing development methods have to be adapted (Isaksson et al. 2009; Rennpferdt und Krause 2020). In summary, this leads to the current situation: specialists from different disciplines and departments are involved in the process of developing

modular product families. The interaction of the various departments and disciplines creates challenges in the course of modularization, but it can also open up potential for innovative solutions.

In this paper, the "Research Background" is discussed first. It briefly describes the underlying survey, the cross-departmental and cross-disciplinary considerations, and the development of mechatronic systems towards cyber-physical mechatronic systems. Then, in the section of "Methodology and Research Questions", the approach and data basis of the survey are described. In doing so, this publication is placed in the overall context of the survey. In addition, based on the research and findings from the first part of the survey, two research questions are posed, which are answered in the sections that follow. After describing the basis for the research presented here, the Results section describes and visualizes the results of the survey. These results are critically examined in the subsequent section in order to provide a discussion of the results and an outlook for further research in the concluding section.

Research Background

This publication is based on a previously by the authors conducted industry study, the first, general part of which was published in (Zuefle et al. 2021). This publication identifies relevant product development challenges prioritized by the survey participants. The implications for modular product development presented here refer to the challenges and trends identified in (Zuefle et al. 2021). In addition, this publication refers to aspects of cross-departmental collaboration for the development of modular product families and their harmonization across different life cycle phases. The topic is described by (Greve et al. 2020) and (Krause et al. 2014). In this context, the development of modular product families is viewed as a cross-departmental task that does not cover just one viewpoint but brings department-specific requirements into the process. There is no module structure that covers all the requirements of all product life phases, but rather a module structure that represents a compromise of all the departments involved. In the process, the compromises are formed in harmonization (Greve et al. 2020; Krause et al. 2014).

In order to additionally link the study to cross-disciplinary collaboration and consider it in relation to the development of modular product families, various publications on interdisciplinary structures also serve a relevant literature base. Jungert (2013) and C. Jooß et al (2014) provide a good basis for gaining an understanding of interdisciplinarity, multi-disciplinarity and cross-disciplinarity. It is noticeable that there are different levels of collaboration in these terms, which range from parallel work (multi-disciplinarity) to a close exchange of results and methods (cross-disciplinarity). For this reason, the close exchange of methods and results is of interest for the research conducted here, which is why cross-disciplinarity is considered further (Jungert 2013; Jooß et al. 2014).

In addition, (Oh et al. 2019) deals with cross-domain variety management but focuses mainly on the complexity of the interactions between components and considers them exclusively in three life phases. In doing so, (Oh et al. 2019) refers to various sources that also consider a cross-domain view to build an architecture for product families. (Du et al. 2001), for example, introduced the Architecture for Product Families, which is based on the "marketing," "engineering," and "manufacturing" views. Another example is (Harlou 2006) who considers the three views "Customer", "Engineering" and "Part View" in his Product Family Master Plan. These are all examples of the relevance of looking at cross-departmental opportunities, but usually only slightly touch on cross-disciplinary collaboration. One source that goes to the discipline level in its consideration is C. Askhøj et al. (2021). It presents MESA (Mechanics, Electrics and Software Architecture), a modularization tool. MESA makes it possible to map the overlapping architecture between mechanics, electrics and software in order to break down the silo thinking in the development disciplines and thus generate potentials (Askhøj et al. 2021).

For the motivation of the industry study literature is also consulted, which deals with the increasing complexity of the development of technical systems, in which also the meaning of cyber-physical systems is taken up. Cyber-physical systems or, in a cross-disciplinary context, cyber-physical mechatronic systems, are significantly more software-intensive and service-oriented than previous mechatronic systems. This means that new skills and thought processes are also necessary in the development of such systems, which can be supported in the form of methods, models, or tools (Tomiyama et al. 2019). Today's systems are also changing in their composition of discipline-related scopes. Thus, the software and electronics part of a system increases significantly and the mechanical part loses importance for the overall functionality of the system (Eigner et al. 2014).

Through the previously conducted literature review, no unified literature base on cross-disciplinary collaboration was identified. This does not mean that there is a gap, but offers a motivation to query such structures in practice. Furthermore, an insufficient reference of cross-disciplinary and cross-departmental structures in the context of modular product families was uncovered, which will be supported in this research by practical statements.

Methodology and Research Questions

For this publication, the authors conducted an industry study on the challenges and potentials in the practice of product development, in which different R&D experts from different industries were queried (Zuefle et al. 2021). The first and general part of the industry survey serves as the basis for this paper. This first part addresses e.g., the data basis of the survey and current situation in team collaboration. Following the identified challenges and potentials of product development are placed into the context of developing modular product families in this research. Through the expertise of the survey participants, specific challenges are named and potentials are identified in the context of cross-departmental and cross-disciplinary collaboration. In conclusion the identified potentials of cross-departmental and cross-disciplinary collaboration were depicted and discussed before an outlook on further research needs was given. Figure 1 illustrates the structure of the survey and the incorporation of the previous research addressed, as well as the research considered in this publication.

Figure 1 - overall survey structure as basis for this research including M. Zuefle et al. (2021).

The underlying survey was conducted with a participation of n=36 industry participants. The experts came from various industries and company sizes. The proportion of survey participants from research and development in machinery and equipment engineering (55%) predominates, but participants from a wide range of sectors, e.g., from aerospace (3%) and shipbuilding (6%) to automotive manufacturers (3%) and

suppliers (6%), contributed expertise to the survey. 55% of the experts interviewed came from large-sized companies with more than 5000 employees, 13% from companies with 1000 to 5000 employees, 13% from companies with 25 to 999 employees. The remaining 19% came from medium-sized companies up to 249 employees. 70% of the participants had a professional experience of more than 3 years in the surveyed field. Thereby 33% of the respondents even had a professional experience of more than 10 years.

For the further consideration of the results in the context of the development of modular product families approximately 66% of the asked participants have stated experience in this topic, which enables them to contribute into the subsequent inquiries. Subsequently, the potentials, advantages and challenges of modular product family strategies were queried in order to be able to gain information about how modular product families can benefit in practice and what are the obstacles in utilizing the full potential. Thereafter potentials and necessary steps of cross-disciplinary structures in the development of modular product families were inquired.

Due to the methodology in this research and the depicted research background there are two research questions guiding through this publication:

1. What are the challenges in practical development of modular product families?
2. How can these challenges be addressed through cross-departmental and cross-disciplinary collaboration?

These two questions will be answered with the given input from the experts. While in the section “Results” the given answers and derived outputs about the challenges are discussed and depicted, in section “Critical Reflection” these results are taken into a critical context of cross-departmental and cross-disciplinary product development. This critical reflection is used to derive potential impacts and actions for implementing and strengthen those perspectives in developing modular product families.

Results

Based on the numerous statements from industry experts, the evaluation of the survey responses was able to provide interesting conclusions about the challenges in the development of modular product families and at the same time the identification of potential cross-departmental and cross-disciplinary structures and collaboration.

The structure of the survey, as shown in Figure 1, first dealt with the topic of developing modular product families from a general perspective so that these findings could then be placed in the context of cross-disciplinary and cross-departmental collaboration in a second sequence.

Figure 2 - Design Strategy by Participants in [%]

Before this, however, the participants were asked what type of development strategy is used in their company in order to be able to assess the participating experts and their knowledge in the development or use of modular product families. The participants were given the opportunity to select several answer options, as a company does not always use just one strategy, but often employs a mix of development strategies. The result is visualized in Figure 2 and shows a high level of participation by practical experts who have experience with the development of modular product families. It should be noted here that only around 10% of the participants were exclusively involved in special development. It was therefore possible to draw on a broad spectrum of experts from the development of modular product families or similar processes.

To enable cross-departmental and cross-disciplinary structures to be considered in the development of modular product families, a survey was first carried out to gauge the mood regarding the development of modular product families. The advantages, challenges, and potentials of the development of modular product families were discussed, as visualized in Figure 1 (Block 3). The input collected on the three points mentioned is presented and described in the following sections. The survey participants were able to respond in a free-text field. These answers were then categorized as shown in Figure 3 and sorted according to their frequency.

Figure 3 - Process of clustering and visualizing the input from practical experts

First, the experts were asked about the advantages of developing modular product families as opposed to special developments and standardized products. These results are visualized in Figure 4.

Figure 4 - Input from practical experts regarding advantages of modular product families

In conclusion, it can be said that the results obtained are consistent with advantages observed in the literature. For example, Hackl et al. (2020) can be referenced.

In order to map not only the advantages but also the challenges of developing modular product families, the experts were also asked about the challenges posed by such a strategy. The scheme in Figure 3 was

again used to sort and analyze the input from the experts. The various clusters of challenges can be seen in Figure 5.

Figure 5 - Input from practical experts regarding challenges in developing modular product families

Figure 5 shows that there are various challenges that can be addressed through cross-disciplinary and cross-departmental collaboration. The first five points in Figure 5 can be taken as an example. “*Prioritizing and summarizing customer requirements*” as well as “*gaining acceptance in the organization*” are challenges that can be supported by cross-departmental collaboration. “*Overarching requirements*”, the “*module cut*”, and “*communication and infrastructure*” are also challenges that can be addressed through both cross-disciplinary and cross-departmental collaboration. More information on this can also be found in Zuefle et al. (2021), in which challenges to product development are considered in more detail.

To conclude the general question section on the development of modular product families, the practical experts were also asked about the potentials of this strategy. In this way, not only the advantages and challenges from practice can be mapped and documented, but also the potentials and opportunities that arise as a result. The potentials are shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6 - Input from practical experts regarding potentials in developing modular product families

In the case of potentials, the significance of the frequency with which they are named is significantly lower than in the two previous figures. The reason for this is that each expert sees different potentials as a result

of his or her experience. Thus, all the potentials presented were examined by us with the same importance.

The potentials presented and obtained by the practitioners can all be transferred to collaboration at cross-departmental and cross-disciplinary level after close examination. This already gives an impression of the synergy of overarching methods and approaches in the development of modular product families. "*Visualization/Communication*", "*Higher Integration of Customer Requirements*" and "*Interface Consideration Essential for Mechatronics*" from Figure 6 are taken as examples.

"*Visualization/Communication*" is a highly generic point, but it refers to an essential basis for collaboration. Specifically, the common understanding of the system under consideration. This understanding also needs to be formed across all stakeholders involved and thus includes cross-discipline and cross-departmental exchanges to map the understanding.

"*Higher Integration of Customer Requirements*" indicates not only the direction of individualization in the development of modular product families, but also the validation of the system to be developed and manufactured throughout the entire life phases. Thus, the cross-departmental perspective is an important aspect for communicating customer requirements across the various departments. In addition, networked cross-disciplinary structures enable the developed systems to become more adaptable and changeable. One example is the use of additional software, which influences the functionality of a system and is also less expensive to customize than mechanical components.

"*Interface Consideration Essential for Mechatronics*" is another exemplary point that refers to cross-disciplinary and cross-departmental structures. There are some parallels to "*Visualization/Communication*", but the focus is more on the communication of dependencies of the different stakeholders. Through approaches of cross-disciplinary and cross-departmental collaboration, this documentation can be used as a "single source of truth".

Figure 7 - Fitness of modular development and cross-disciplinary and -departmental collaboration

In addition, the indicated challenges to the development of modular product families are analyzed and set into the context of the cross-disciplinary collaboration around to examine whether thereby possible solution potentials point out. Simultaneously these challenges are set additionally into the context of the cross-departmental collaboration and the method of life phase modularization to analyze also potential synergies by integration of several life phases.

Subsequently to the previous query the survey participants were asked if cross-disciplinary is relevant for dealing with current and future challenges in developing modular product families. After dealing with advantages, challenges and potentials of modular development the queried experts were incorporated into the field of possible synergies. The results are shown in Figure 7.

Furthermore, the survey explicitly targeted the opinions and assessments of the experts as to what potential can be created by the synergy between cross-disciplinary and cross-departmental structures in the development of modular product families. A summary of the responses is shown in the list below. No clustering or similar was carried out, but the comments of the participants were listed in order to distort the results as little as possible.

- As complete as possible **decoupling of flows and functions** in a module requires the know-how from all areas (cross-departmental + cross-disciplinary). Better **alternative estimation for module cutting**
- Support of the later **self-image in the organization** (product as collaboration of all disciplines and departments)
- Sensible limitation and standardization of **external interfaces**
- Close coordination between disciplines indispensable, since the **components come from different disciplines**.
- As **complete as possible mapping of the requirement** through cross-departmental and cross-disciplinary collaboration. **Holistic picture** of the system (incl. interactions).
- Better **combinability of modules** through collaboration of several disciplines. Compatibility on several levels.
- Only in this way can **modularization be used holistically**. Otherwise silo thinking would only be postponed.
- To provide a module completely it requires cross-disciplinarity, since only in such a way the **system cut** can be accomplished optimized.
- **Rapid development** through cross-discipline collaboration and **exchange**.
- **Views of modules are so different** across disciplines and departments that cross-disciplinarity is essential. This is a **basic condition for plug-and-play**.
- **Interfaces are interdisciplinary** and must be documented and maintained as such.
- These structures are **prerequisites for modularization**, since modular products require interdisciplinary coordination and **bundled know-how**.
- **Mechatronic systems are interdisciplinary** and can only be mapped as a whole in this way.
- Interdisciplinary properties make the **holistic functions of a product available**.

As a result of the elaboration, various advantages and potentials of cross-departmental and cross-disciplinary collaboration are pointed out. The potentials are classified on the basis of the respondents' statements about their current way of working, into potentials that both have already been implemented and are in the process of being implemented, as well as potentials that are to be implemented in the future. This classification also leads to the research priorities derived from the survey in order to support the development of complicated and complex structures in the context of modular product families.

Discussion and Outlook

The results shown represent only a small fraction of what can and should be identified through further research. However, it already shows a general outline of the extent to which the development of modular product families should at least consider opportunities for the integration of cross-disciplinary and cross-departmental collaboration. It is necessary, however, to distinguish and separate cross-disciplinary and cross-departmental collaboration. The cross-departmental collaboration is already well supported e.g., by

Paper submitted to and accepted after peer-review:

R&D Management Conference 2021 "Innovation in an Era of Disruption"; July 6th-8th 2021, Glasgow, SCO

the method of Life Phase Modularization according to (Krause et al. 2014) and has been validated in practice many times. Whereas cross-disciplinary collaboration in the development of modular product families still requires further investigation. On the one hand, the responses of the practitioners are highly informative regarding the expectations they have of collaboration across disciplinary boundaries, but there were no indications in the responses as to how this collaboration could be supported. Nevertheless, the experts surveyed are almost unanimous that cross-disciplinary collaboration is or will be a crucial part of the development of modular product families. For this reason, the survey not only provides some insight into what should be achieved through more intensive exchange between disciplines, but also that the exchange should be intensified in future. It can be deduced from this that support for such structures is or will also be relevant.

Practitioners from industry can reference the results of this paper to their company. This will give them a basis to evaluate whether cross-disciplinary and cross-disciplinary collaboration is helpful for them and if so, to what extent it should be implemented.

Literature

Askhøj, Christoffer; Christensen, Carsten Keinicke Fjord; Mortensen, Niels Henrik (2021): Cross domain modularization tool: Mechanics, electronics, and software. In: *Concurrent Engineering*, 1063293X2110003. DOI: 10.1177/1063293X211000331.

Blecker, Thorsten; Abdelkafi, Nizar (2006): Complexity and variety in mass customization systems: analysis and recommendations. In: *Management Decision* 44 (7), S. 908–929. DOI: 10.1108/00251740610680596.

Du, Xuehong; Jiao, Jianxin; Tseng, Mitchell M. (2001): Architecture of Product Family: Fundamentals and Methodology. In: *Concurrent Engineering* 9 (4), S. 309–325. DOI: 10.1177/1063293X0100900407.

Eigner, Martin; Roubanov, Daniil; Zafirov, Radoslav (2014): Modellbasierte virtuelle Produktentwicklung. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg.

Greve, Erik; Rennpferdt, Christoph; Krause, Dieter (2020): Harmonizing cross-departmental Perspectives on Modular Product Families. In: *Procedia CIRP* 91, S. 452–457. DOI: 10.1016/j.procir.2020.02.198.

Hackl, Jennifer; Krause, Dieter; Otto, Kevin; Windheim, Marc; Moon, Seung Ki; Bursac, Nikola; Lachmayer, Roland (2020): Impact of Modularity Decisions on a Firm's Economic Objectives. In: *Journal of Mechanical Design* 142 (4). DOI: 10.1115/1.4044914.

Harlou, Ulf (2006): Developing product families based on architectures. Contribution to a theory of product families. Lyngby: Department of Mechanical Engineering, Technical University of Denmark.

Isaksson, Ola; Larsson, Tobias C.; Rönnbäck, Anna Öhrwall (2009): Development of product-service systems: challenges and opportunities for the manufacturing firm. In: *Journal of Engineering Design* 20 (4), S. 329–348. DOI: 10.1080/09544820903152663.

Jooß, Claudia; Welter, Florian; Leisten, Ingo; Richert, Anja; Jeschke, Sabina (2014): Innovationsförderliches Knowledge Engineering in inter- und transdisziplinären Forschungsverbänden. In: Manfred Mai (Hg.): *Handbuch Innovationen*. Wiesbaden: Springer Fachmedien Wiesbaden, S. 105–119.

Jungert, Michael (Hg.) (2013): *Interdisziplinarität. Theorie, Praxis, Probleme*. 2., durchges. und um ein aktuelles Vorw. erw. Ausg. Darmstadt: WBG (Wiss. Buchges.).

Krause, Dieter; Beckmann, Gregor; Eilmus, Sandra; Gebhardt, Nicolas; Jonas, Henry; Rettberg, Robin (2014): Integrated Development of Modular Product Families: A Methods Toolkit. In: Timothy W. Simpson, Jianxin Jiao, Zahed Siddique und Katja Hölttä-Otto (Hg.): *Advances in Product Family and*

Paper submitted to and accepted after peer-review:

R&D Management Conference 2021 "Innovation in an Era of Disruption"; July 6th-8th 2021, Glasgow, SCO

Product Platform Design. Methods & applications. New York, NY: Springer New York (Advances in Product Family and Product Platform Design), S. 245–269.

Krause, Dieter; Gebhardt, Nicolas (2018): Methodische Entwicklung modularer Produktfamilien. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg.

Oh, Kwansuk; Lim, Jong Wook; Cho, Seongwon; Ryu, Junyeol; Hong, Yoo S. (2019): A Framework for Development Architecture for Modular Products: Cross-Domain Variety Management Perspective. In: *Proc. Int. Conf. Eng. Des.* 1 (1), S. 2921–2930. DOI: 10.1017/dsi.2019.299.

Otto, Kevin; Hölttä-Otto, Katja; Simpson, Timothy W.; Krause, Dieter; Ripperda, Sebastian; Ki Moon, Seung (2016): Global Views on Modular Design Research: Linking Alternative Methods to Support Modular Product Family Concept Development. In: *Journal of Mechanical Design* 138 (7). DOI: 10.1115/1.4033654.

Rennpferdt, C.; Krause, D. (2020): Towards a Framework for the Design of variety-oriented Product-Service Systems. In: *Proc. Des. Soc.: Des. Conf.* 1, S. 1345–1354. DOI: 10.1017/dsd.2020.108.

Ripperda, Sebastian; Krause, Dieter (2017): Cost Effects of Modular Product Family Structures: Methods and Quantification of Impacts to Support Decision Making. In: *Journal of Mechanical Design* 139 (2). DOI: 10.1115/1.4035430.

Tomiyaama, Tetsuo; Lutters, Eric; Stark, Rainer; Abramovici, Michael (2019): Development capabilities for smart products. In: *CIRP Annals* 68 (2), S. 727–750. DOI: 10.1016/j.cirp.2019.05.010.

Zuefle, Marc; Rennpferdt, Christoph; Krause, Dieter (2021): Cross-departmental and cross-disciplinary product development – An industry survey on the necessity and future development of cross-departmental and cross-disciplinary perspectives. In: *Procedia CIRP* 100, S. 625–630. DOI: 10.1016/j.procir.2021.05.147.